

Conflict Management Between Parents and Children: The Role of Counselling

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Abstract

The parent-child relationship is one of the most trust-worthy relationships of a society. It is one of the long lasting social ties among human beings and a pillar for forming family. But a very common problem most times to every family irrespective of its social, financial status is conflicts between parents and children, which is an aspect of the parent-child relationship that is characterized by discordant and acrimonious interactions during which both the parent and child display negative behaviours and affect. Many times, it is visible and many times, it is invisible. Factors which turnout to be the causes of this conflict are parental expectations related to discipline and understanding family responsibilities, academic performance, children purported parents interference in their private lives, focusing on bad behaviours exhibited at all times without noticing and encouraging good behaviour sometimes among others. This paper examines the management of conflict between parents and children as well as the role of counselling as an intervention strategy. The paper also recommended counselling as a veritable tool for effective and efficient improvement plan in cushioning the effects of conflict between parents and children.

Keywords: Conflict, Management, Parents, Children, Counselling.

Introduction

Conflict is used in so many ways in our day-to-day setup. In any given day, week, month and year, more than 20 cases of violent conflicts of different kinds occur around the world, most of which are in developing countries of Asia and Africa (Stockholm International Peace Research Institute 'SIPRI', 2000). There may be conflicts between two sets of ideologies, cultures, religions and organizations. Conflicts may arise between husband and wife, father and son, teacher and

the taught. It may also show its presence among brothers and sisters, members of an organization or community, states of a country and countries of the world at large (Mangal, 2007). Again, mothers were reported to have higher levels of conflict with their children than did fathers. It may be because mothers spend a greater amount of time with their children during early childhood and therefore have a greater opportunity to experience conflict in their relationships than do fathers (Child Psychiatry Human Department, 2016).

However, apart from these external or outer conflicts, there are inner or internal conflicts which are called 'psychological conflicts'. More so, conflict can arise between members of the same group known as intra group conflict, or it can occur between members of two or more groups and involve violence, interpersonal discord, and psychological tension, known as intergroup conflict. Conflict in groups often follows a specific course. Routine group interaction is first disrupted by an initial conflict, often caused by differences of opinion, disagreements between members, or scarcity of resources. The effects of these conflicts are manifested in the disruption of lives and usual daily routines, public infrastructure such as roads, schools, health institutions among others, violation of the fundamental human rights of civilians and most especially those of the children. At this point, the group is no longer united, and may split into coalitions.

This period of conflict escalation in some cases gives way to a conflict resolution stage, after which the group can eventually return to routine group interaction once again. However, Action Health Incorporated 'AHI', (2002) noted that conflict between parents could devastate the child because such conflicts may have lasting impact on the child's psychology. Conflict is therefore better resolved than encouraged.

This paper therefore attempts to examine the areas of conflicts between parents and children: the role of counselling. To achieve this objective therefore, the writers discussed the following scheme;

- I. Concept of conflict and parent-child conflict
- II. Causes/Areas of Conflict between parents and children
- III. The effect of conflicts between parent and children
- IV. Conflict resolution/management
- V. The role of counselling
- VI. Summary/Conclusion
- VII. Recommendations

Conflicts refers to some form of friction, disagreement or discord arising within a group when the beliefs or actions of one or more members of the group are either resisted by or unacceptable to one or more members of another group. Conflict is also seen as a clash between individuals arising out of a difference in thought process, attitudes, understanding, interests, requirements and even sometimes perceptions (Juneja, 2015).

Corroborating the above definitions, conflict can also be defined as a state of affairs in which two or more incompatible behaviour trends cannot be satisfied fully at the same time. Juneja (2015) opined that conflict has five phases namely; prelude to conflict, triggering event, initiation phase, Differentiation phase and Resolution phase.

These definitions help us to conclude according to Mangal (2007) that;

- Conflict is a painful state or condition of an individual.
- One feels intense emotional tension during this state.
- Tension is the result of the presence of two or more desires or wishes in the individual. These desires are contradictory in nature and therefore cannot be satisfied fully at the same time.
- The individual, being at the crossroads and not able to choose between the two opposing desires, becomes tense and restless.
- Thus becoming a victim of the two opposing desires, he suffers from an inner conflict to do or not to satisfy one or the other desire.

Conflict as noted by Tyav and Tarbunde (2009) is a natural and necessary part of people's lives, an inevitable feature of domestic and international relations. In realizing this, governments, corporate bodies, the civil society, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) among others are often confronted with not just the issue of eliminating conflicts, which is not even feasible, but rather how to effectively adopt a potent and effective conflict resolution strategy, where it occurs.

Causes /Areas of Conflict between Parents and Children

A list of factors is responsible for conflict, but the root cause is 'Difference'. Difference in opinions and ways of expressing, difference of personality, differences in career options available to the child, difference in dressing, difference in choice of friends, difference in a set bed time, type of Television/Video programmes to watch, difference in outing/parties/Dating, difference in driving, sibling rivalry, choice of school and religious beliefs among others (Action Health Incorporated Manual, 2002).

Moreso, conflicting messages can also cause conflict, in that some parents may tell their children what to do but do different things. This type of attitude tend to send wrong signals to their children. An example is irresponsible sexual behaviour from either of the parents. Other possible areas of conflict could be choice of music, choice of life partner and other related issues. Furthermore, faulty upbringing at home, unhealthy or unpleasant relationship among the family members are the potential sources of conflict in children. A child, due to over protection, dominance, submissiveness or negligence on the part of parents, does not cope with the experiences during social contacts with other children at school and thus he may become a victim of the opposing desires in future.

In the same vein, we have seen that conflicts are the creation of the dissatisfaction felt by an individual due to the non-fulfillment of his two contradictory desires. The forces of the environment are in fact responsible for these conflicts as they provide necessary ground for their occurrence but at the same time the teachers, parents and society are also responsible for giving birth to so many conflicts in our youngsters (Mangal, 2007).

A latest study has revealed that most parents and children experience some conflicts and tension with each other, in which parents are more prone to tension, and the older the child, the greater the bothering of tension.

Similarly, other factors which turnout to be causes of conflicts between parents and children are:

- Parental expectations related to discipline, like social customs, moral values, choice of friends, time management among others.
- Parental expectations related to understanding family responsibilities like family works, family relationships, and money management among others.
- Academic performance including study habits and other related issues.
- Perception by children that parents are less caring, taking away his freedom, less communicating, less inductive, but more indulgent and exactly opposite perception of parents.
- Children think that parents interfere in their private life. It is more common in teenagers who do not want to share their life. For them, it is meant to be outside of his/her parent's authority (Juneja, 2015).

The Outcome of Conflicts between Parents and Children

A small conflict not controlled at the correct time may lead to a large war. Misunderstanding and ego clashes can lead to conflict. Every individual has a different way to look at things and react to various situations (<https://www.managementstudyguide.com> 2017). Hence, reactions not cautiously done can breed conflict with its negative effects on the parents involved.

Conflict is not good to be encouraged between parents and children because when it occurs, the two parties will never rapport. There will not be happiness in the house. Rebellion will be the order of the day. There will not be free flow of communication. Parents can no longer communicate the cultural values to the children and they may be behaving abnormally as they like. Juvenile delinquency will become paramount. There will be no respect meted to each parties. There will be chaos/anarchy/confusion in the home. They will prefer staying away from the home most of the time because the home will not be conducive for any of the parties.

Consequently, children may be misinformed. They may be bombarded with wrong messages from television, advertisements, music, friends, books and magazines as parents are not relating well with the children. The children will exhibit disobedience most times even if they correct them. They will be less concerned. The parents will no longer be free to discharge their responsibilities of correcting, interpreting or corroborating information from outside sources to them. They cannot share beliefs and concerns with them effectively. The parents can no longer be trusted and vice versa. According to Kelly in Keuhnle and Drozd (2012) children are in most cases deprived of quality education and health care, and left with deep emotional scars and trauma. This experience sometimes leads to dropping out of school by some school children. Such children sometimes loom about in the streets, develop bad behaviours and follow bad gangs. They are being exposed to all forms of danger including recruitment into evil groups like armed robbery, kidnapping, Indian hemp smokers cultism among others. These children sometimes become very vulnerable. Girls face additional risks, particularly sexual violence and exploitation. All of these categories of children are victims of conflict between parents and children. All of them deserve the attention and protection of their parents.

Furthermore, parents are being stressed up both psychologically and emotionally. Some of them develop hypertension (BP) problem and in extreme cases die out of the trauma they are passing through with their children. Parents are in most cases at variance with people they relate with because they lack peace of mind. They behave as if they are fighting with themselves. Their words and actions are at times detestable.

However, apart from the negative effects of conflict on parents and children, there are a few positive ones. Conflict between parents and children sometimes have a deterrent effect on both of them. It makes them to be conscious of their behaviour most times so as to avoid having problem with either their parents or children as the case may be. They become more careful and thoughtful before acting among others.

Conflict Resolution/Management

Great relationships develop not from the absence of conflict but from determining an agreeable pattern for how to resolve conflict. Defining the rules of engagement for how you “fight” with someone you care about is ultimately much more important than trying to never have a disagreement. Conflict is a social process that is exacerbated when individual members of a group take sides in the debate. It can therefore be resolved when the inconsistency between wishes and actions of parties are resolved (Nicholson, 2005).

However, all the factors leading to a fight must be explored and efforts must be made to prevent a conflict, though it is not very easy to control without possession of adequate skills. According to Juneja (2015), the skills include: effective communication skills, listening skills, discussion, patience, being impartial, never criticize, positive attitude and ignoring others. Furthermore, Forsyth (2006) stated that among the methods to resolve conflict is mediation of the dispute by a group member not currently involved in the dispute. He stressed that a mediator is a person who attempts to resolve a conflict between two parties by intervening in the conflict. The mediator can also offer assistance in refining solutions and making counter offers between members, adjusting the time and location of meetings so that they are mutually satisfying for both parties.

In addition this type of conflict can be resolved through so many ways including laughter. Laughter is the best medicine, and it is true. Laughter relieves tension, soothes away pains and stress, raises mood, enhances creativity and boosts energy. Laughter also plays an important role in building strong, healthy relationships by bringing people closer together, creating intimacy and resolving conflict and disagreements (Between Man & Woman, 2014)

In the same vein, humor, judiciously used can effectively defuse conflict. Once stress and emotion are brought into balance, one’s capacity for joy, pleasure and playfulness is unleashed. Joy is a deceptively powerful resource. According to Between Man & Woman (2014), one can surmount adversity as long as he continues to have moments of joy. Hence, humor plays a similar role when facing conflict. One can avoid many confrontations and resolve arguments and disagreements by communicating in a humorous way. It further stressed that humor can help one say things that might otherwise be difficult to express without offending someone. However,

it is important that one laughs with the other person, not at them. When humor and play are used to reduce tension and anger, reframe problems, and put the situation into perspective, the conflict can actually become an opportunity for greater connection and intimacy.

Moreso, successful conflict resolution depends on one's ability to regulate stress and emotions. Arguing with your child(ren) is no fun. It can stress out both parties (<https://www.goodtherapy.org> 2018). Conflict triggers strong emotions and can lead to hurt feelings, disappointment and discomfort. When handled in an unhealthy manner, it can cause irreparable rifts, resentments and breakups.

But when conflict is resolved in a healthy way, it increases our understanding of one another, builds trust and strengthens our relationship bonds. It is also important to note that managing stress demands that one remains alert and calm. This is because by staying calm, one can accurately read and interpret verbal and non-verbal communication. He can control his emotions and behaviour which can help him to communicate his needs without threatening, frightening or punishing others. He will also be able to pay attention to the feelings being expressed as well as the spoken words of others. He will also be aware of and respectful of differences by avoiding disrespectful words and actions which can almost always resolve a problem faster (Between Man & Woman, 2014).

Furthermore, Nicholson (2005) stated that emotional awareness is one of the core conflict resolution skills. It is the key to understanding oneself and others. If one does not know how he feels or why he feels that way, he would not be able to communicate effectively or resolve disagreements. Emotional awareness as the consciousness of one's moment to moment emotional experience – and the ability to manage all of one's feelings appropriately is the basis of a communication process that can resolve conflict. Hence, it can help one to:

- Understand what is really troubling other people
- Understand oneself, including what is really troubling him.
- Stay motivated until the conflict is resolved
- Communicate clearly and effectively
- Attract and influence others.

It is therefore pertinent that one should have the ability to remain comfortable enough with his emotions to be able to react in constructive ways even in the midst of an argument or a perceived attack.

In conflict resolution also, non-verbal communication plays a big role. During conflicts, the most important information exchanged is often communicated nonverbally. The most important communication is wordless. According to Forsyth (2006), when people are upset, the words they use rarely convey the issues and needs at the heart of the problem. When one listens for what is felt- as well as what is said – he connects more deeply to our own needs and emotions, and to those of other people. Listening in this way also strengthens us, informs us, and makes it easier for others to hear us, he stressed.

Explaining further, he noted that when one is in the middle of a conflict, paying close attention to the other person's nonverbal signals may help him figure out what the other person

is really saying. This will allow him to respond in a way that builds trust and gets to the root of the problem. A calm tone of voice, a reassuring touch, or an interested or concerned facial expression can go a long way toward relaxing a tense exchange. Kelly in Kuehnle and Drozd (2012) noted that resolving conflict has shown to positively help children and protect them from the negative effects of parent conflict.

The Role of Counselling

When conflicts arise, they can be resolved constructively through conflict resolution training for all involved (Santrock, 2001). The provision of Guidance and Counselling services become paramount here because life is full of conflict. Conflict is inevitable part of all relationships. It may take the form of major discord between two people or simply petty aggravations that have built up over time. (Between Man & Woman, 2014). When conflict and disagreement throw a wrench in a relationship, counselling can help lighten things up and restore a sense of connection. In other words, counselling will enable them make right decisions that will help them in making proper adjustment(s). Thus, a counsellor according to Anagbogu (2002) is a professional who through diagnosing, planning, predicting, interpreting and evaluating provided educational, personal and vocational assistance to the clients in such a way that it would reflect their interests, objectives, potentialities and needs for effective adjustment. The indication is that the counsellor is not only a peace educator, but he is fully engaged in resolving and managing clients conflicts, so that such conflicts would not spill over or be over blown.

Moreso, counselling when skillfully and respectfully applied can help to quickly turn conflict and tension into an opportunity for shared fun and intimacy. It allows one to get his point across without getting the other persons defenses up or hurting his or her feelings.

Counselling will help both parents and children break free from rigid ways of thinking and behaving, allowing them to see the problem in a new way and find a creative solution. Counselling, free of hurtful sarcasm or ridicule neutralizes conflict by helping the parties involved to interrupt the power struggle, instantly easing tension and allowing them to reconnect and regain perspective.

Moreover, counselling has the role of explaining to the parties involved in conflict the dos and don'ts in preventing conflict. For example, parents and children should not yell and cuss at each other. They should not focus on who is right, but on what is right. They should not speak in generalities of another person's behaviour but speak only to direct examples and instances of action. They should try to always work to be the first to apologize when any dispute arises. When thinking about what happened, try to remove yourself from the situation and evaluate right and wrong based solely on the actions that took place regardless of which side you are on. (Between Man & Woman, 2014). Explaining further, it is the role of counselling to let parents understand some basic principles of effective parenting/disciplining their children as well as knowing how they perceive situation so that conflict will be minimized. For example, parents should learn to notice, praise and encourage good behaviour rather than focusing on bad behaviour(s) always (Whitson, 2019). They should establish fair rules, make as few rules as possible and ensure that they are clear, involve children in making the rules if possible, form agreement with children

instead of imposing their will on them and explain why the rules are important, avoid-hitting or spanking the children because it is likely to decrease the quality of your relationship with them, among others (Action Health Incorporated, 2002). It is evident therefore to state that counselling role in resolving conflict is enormous. Counselling maintains peace, encourages peace and creates peace.

Conclusion

A conflict results in heated arguments, physical abuses and definitely loss of peace and harmony. A conflict can actually change relationships. Friends can become foes as a result of conflict. In view of these, efforts have been made to examine conflicts between parents and children and the role of counselling. To achieve this objective therefore, the paper expatiates on the conceptual clarifications on conflict, causes/areas of conflict between parents and children. The outcome of conflicts between parents and their children, conflict resolution/management and the role of counselling have been considered. It has been observed therefore that conflict is a natural phenomenon and necessary part of human life. It is an inevitable and inherent feature in human societies. Conflict is a painful condition or emotionally tense state of an individual reached on account of the presence of the two opposed and contradictory wishes at the same time. Conflicts are thus devastating and could cause problem(s). The paper therefore advocated using peaceful means to manage conflicts instead of quarrels.

The paper also view counselling as a medium of enthroning mutual co-existence free of strife and animosity. It enhances the ability of the parties involved in conflict to acquire skills and knowledge of cooperation, peace and oneness instead of violence. Counselling preaches respect, humility among others and the Counsellor(s) champion(s) the enthronement of peace, decorum, understanding, and cohesion meant for the achievement of mutual co-habitation instead of deprivation, humiliation, abuse and discrimination that may thrive on conflict situation(s).

Recommendations

An extrapolation from the foregoing reveals that conflict between parents and their children could be devastating to both parties and may have lasting impact on their psychology. It is indeed better to live harmoniously.

This paper therefore recommends in line with Action Health Incorporated (2002) that:

- i. Parents should listen to their children's views and discuss all the options. For instance, if a child wants to settle for a career the parent does not like, ask him why, ask him what the advantages of his choice are, as well as the disadvantages, let him read more about the career and discuss with someone who is already in the field and then reach a compromise based on his or her discussions with him or her.
- ii. Parents should endeavour to communicate their own beliefs and values to their children. They should however keep in mind that the children will form their own standards of behaviour, with or without their help. The best way to communicate those values is by showing good example. A child is more likely to listen to his/her

- parent when he shows him/her good example. Parents should be their child's role model. This makes it easy to correct the child when he/she is misbehaving.
- iii. Negotiation with the parties involved is very important. Here, both parties should provide options when necessary and ask the other person to agree with him/her on any of the options. For instance, the parent can say to his child, if you insist on going out with your friends, then I must meet those friends first and have a discussion with them.
 - iv. The parent should let the child know that he is acting in his best interest. He should share his past experiences with the child and let him reason with him. Give the child an opportunity to express his thoughts and feelings about the parent's decision.
 - v. Compromise does not mean defeat. Sometimes, parents need to trust their children to make their own decisions. The parents can provide some level of support, such as adequate transport fare, opportunities to phone them in cases of an emergency and so forth.
 - vi. Community counselling should be introduced in various communities towards replicating the skills of tolerance, obedience, humility, love, peace and understanding among parents and children in the communities. This will help to minimize conflict between parents and children.

REFERENCES

- Action Health Incorporated (2002). *Can we really talk about it? A workshop guide for assisting parents to talk with their adolescents*. Lagos- Nigeria: AIII Publishers.
- Anagbogu, M.A. (2002). *Techniques of counselling: A practical approach to counselling in Nigeria*. Benin City: Olivert Publishing Company Nig.
- Between Man & Woman (2014, July). Using laughter and play to build, maintain successful relationship. *Saturday Sun*, pp. 26.
- Child Psychiatry Human Development PMC. (2016). Parent child conflict and Early childhood Adjustment in Two-Parent low-income families: Parallel Developmental Process.
- Conflict Resolution Manual (2003). Centre for conflict resolution. South Africa: Rondebosh.
- Forsyth, F. (2006). *The Afghan: Thriller novel*. United Kingdom: Bantam Press.
- Jeannette,R.(2018)Five tips to reduce conflict between parents and children. Retrieved from <https://www.goodtherapy.org>Good> on 1st November, 2019.
- Juneja, P. (2015). *Skills to control conflict*: Reviewed by Management study guide content team. Retrieved from <https://www.managementstudyguide.com>understanding-conflict> on the 4th of Novermber,2017.

- Kelly, J. (2012). Risk and protective factors associated with child and adolescent adjustment following separation and divorce. Social Science applications. In K. Kuehnle & Drozd (eds.). *Parenting plan evaluation: Applied research for the family court*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Lexicon Websters Dictionary. (1981). Cleveland, Ohio: John Wiley Publishing, Inc.
- Mangal, S.K. (2007). *Essentials of educational psychology*. New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Private Limited.
- Nicholson, M. (2005). *Conflict resolution and conflict transformation*. New bury Park CA: Sage Publishers.
- Santrock, J.W. (2001). *Educational psychology*. New York: McGraw-Hill Companies, Inc.
- Stockholm International Peace Research Institute, Major Armed Conflict, SIPRI Year Book (2000). Armament, Disarmaments and International Security, SIPRI, Oxford University Press.
- Tyav, T.T., & Torbunde, C.M. (2009). Conflict and child right protection in Nigeria: The Tiv experience. *Benue Journal of Gender Studies*, 1, 64-75.
- Whitson L.S.W. (2019). The Dynamics of conflict between parent and child. Retrieved November 6, 2019 from [https:// www.psychologytoday.com](https://www.psychologytoday.com)